

On Coefficient Estimates for New Subclasses of q -Bi-Spirallike Functions

Read. S. A. Qahtan
 College Of Engineering
 Alrowad University
 Taiz, Yemen

Abstract:- In this paper, we introduce and investigate two new subclasses of the function class $\Sigma @$ of λ - q -bi-spirallike functions defined in the open unit disc. Furthermore, We find estimates on the coefficients

$|a_2|, |a_3|$ and $|a_4|$ for functions in these two new subclasses for functions.

Keywords:- Univalent Functions, Bi-Univalent Functions, q - λ -Spirallike, Subordination, Coefficients Bounds.

I. INTRODUCTION

Let \mathcal{A} denote the class of functions of the form

$$f(z) = z + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} a_n z^n \tag{1}$$

Which are analytic in the open disc $E = \{z: z \in \mathbb{C} \text{ and } |z| < 1\}$. Let \mathcal{S} denote the subclass of function in \mathcal{A} which are univalent in E and indeed normalized by $f(0) = f'(0) - 1 = 0$. It is well known that every function $f \in \mathcal{S}$ has an inverse f^{-1} defined by

$$f^{-1}(f(z)) = z \quad (z \in E),$$

and

$$f(f^{-1}(\omega)) = \omega, \quad (|\omega| < r_0(f), r_0(f) \geq \frac{1}{4})$$

A function $f \in \mathcal{A}$ is said to bi-univalent function in E if f and f^{-1} are together univalent functions in E . Let $\Sigma @$ denote the class of bi-univalent functions defined in E . The inverse function $f^{-1}(\omega)$ is given by

$$h(\omega) = f^{-1}(\omega) = \omega - a_2\omega^2 + (2a_2^2 - a_3)\omega^3 - (5a_3^2 - 5a_2a_3 + a_4)\omega^4 + \dots \tag{2}$$

Spacek [22] introduced the concept of spirallikeness which is a natural generalization of starlikeness. Spirallike functions can be characterized by the following analytic condition:

A function f in \mathcal{A} is λ -spirallik if and only if,

$$\Re \left\{ e^{i\lambda} \frac{zf'(z)}{f(z)} \right\} > 0, \quad z \in E, \tag{3}$$

Where $-\frac{\pi}{2} < \lambda < \frac{\pi}{2}$. In [11], Jackson introduced and studied the concept of the q -derivative operator ∂_q as follows :

$$\partial_q f(z) = \frac{f(z) - f(qz)}{z(1-q)}, \quad (z \neq 0, 0 < q < 1, \partial_q f(0) = f'(0)). \tag{4}$$

Equivalently (4), may be written as

$$\partial_q f(z) = 1 + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} [n]_q a_n z^{n-1}, \quad z \neq 0, \tag{5}$$

Where $[n]_q = \frac{1-q^n}{1-q}$, note that as $q \rightarrow 1^-$, $[n]_q \rightarrow n$.

➤ *Definition 1.1* Let λ - q - $\mathcal{SP}_{\Sigma @}(\sigma)$ denote the class of λ - q -bi-spirallike functions of order σ , ($|\lambda| \leq \pi/2, 0 \leq \sigma < 1$). The function $f(z)$, given by (1), is said it is in λ - q - $\mathcal{SP}_{\Sigma @}(\sigma)$ if it satisfies:

$$f \in \Sigma \text{ @and } \Re \left(e^{i\lambda} \frac{z \partial_q f(z)}{f(z)} \right) > \sigma \cos \lambda \quad (z \in E), \quad (6)$$

and

$$\Re \left(e^{i\lambda} \frac{\omega \partial_q h(\omega)}{h(\omega)} \right) > \sigma \cos \lambda \quad (\omega \in E). \quad (7)$$

➤ **2 Main Results**

➤ *Theorem 2.1* Let $f(z) = z + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} a_n z^n$
 Be in λ - q - $\mathcal{SP}_{\Sigma @}^{\beta}$, ($|\lambda| \leq \frac{\pi}{2}, 0 \leq \beta < 1$). Then

$$|a_2| \leq \frac{2\beta}{\sqrt{((2[3]_q - [2]_q^2 - 1)\beta + ([2]_q - 1)^2)}} \sqrt{\cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)}$$

$$|a_3| \leq \begin{cases} \frac{2\beta}{[3]_q - 1} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right), & 0 \leq \beta \leq \frac{[2]_q - 1}{[2]_q + 1}, \\ \frac{4\beta^2}{((2[2]_q - 1)^2 + (2[3]_q - [2]_q([2]_q - 1) - 3)\beta)} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right), & \frac{[2]_q - 1}{[2]_q + 1} \leq \beta \leq 1. \end{cases}$$

$$|a_4| \leq \begin{cases} \frac{2\beta}{[4]_q - 1} \left[1 - \frac{2}{3} A_1 \sqrt{\cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \right], & 0 < \beta < A, \\ \frac{2\beta}{[4]_q - 1} \left[1 + \frac{2}{3} A_1 \sqrt{\cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \right], & A \leq \beta < A_4, \\ \frac{2\beta}{[4]_q - 1} \left[\frac{((2[2]_q - 1)^3 (5[4]_q + 2[3]_q[2]_q - 4[3]_q - 2[2]_q - 1) + L)}{((2[2]_q - 1)^3 (5[4]_q - 4[3]_q - 2[2]_q + 1)\beta + 2([3]_q - 1))} + \frac{2}{3} A_1 \sqrt{\cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \right], & A_4 \leq \beta \leq 1, \end{cases}$$

Where

$$L = (2([3]_q + [2]_q) - ([3]_q[2]_q + 4))$$

$$A = \frac{3([2]_q - 1)(2[3]_q - [2]_q^2 - 1) + \sqrt{(36[3]_q^2 + [2]_q^4 + 42[2]_q^2 + 8[2]_q^3 + 73) - A_5}}{4(3[3]_q[2]_q + 3[2]_q - [2]_q^3 - 8)}$$

$$A_1 = \frac{2(2(3[3]_q[2]_q + 3[2]_q - [2]_q^3 - 8)\beta^2 - 3([2]_q - 1)(2[3]_q - [2]_q^2 - 1)\beta - ([2]_q - 1)^3)}{3([2]_q - 1)^3 \sqrt{((2[2]_q - 1)^2 + (2[3]_q - [2]_q^2 - 1))}}$$

$$A_4 = \frac{([3]_q[2]_q - [2]_q - [3]_q + 1)}{[3]_q[2]_q}$$

$$A_5 = 12[3]_q[2]_q^2 - 36[3]_q - 88[2]_q - 24[3]_q[2]_q.$$

Proof. Let

$$e^{i\lambda} \frac{z \partial_q f(z)}{f(z)} = g(z) \quad (z \in E, -\frac{\pi}{2} \beta < \lambda < \frac{\pi}{2} \beta), \quad (9)$$

$g(z)$ is analytic in E and satisfies $g(0) = e^{i\lambda}$ and $|\arg g(z)| < \frac{\pi}{2} \beta$ ($z \in E$). It can be checked that the function $\varphi(z)$ defined by:

$$g(z)^{\frac{1}{\beta}} = \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) \varphi(z) + i \sin\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right), \quad (z \in E),$$

Is a member of the class \mathcal{P} .

Let $\varphi(z) = 1 + d_1z + d_2z^2 + \dots, (z \in E)$.

By comparing coefficient in (9), we have

$$a_2 = \frac{\beta d_1 e^{-i(\frac{\lambda}{\beta})}}{[2]_q - 1} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right), \quad (10)$$

$$([3]_q - 1)a_3 - ([2]_q - 1)a_2^2 = \beta d_2 e^{-i(\frac{\lambda}{\beta})} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) + \frac{\beta(\beta-1)}{2} d_1^2 e^{-2i(\frac{\lambda}{\beta})} \cos^2\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right), \quad (11)$$

$$([4]_q - 1)a_4 - D a_2 a_3 + ([2]_q - 1)a_2^3 = \beta d_3 e^{-i(\frac{\lambda}{\beta})} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) + \beta(\beta-1) d_1 d_2 e^{-2i(\frac{\lambda}{\beta})} \cos^2\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) + \frac{\beta(\beta-1)(\beta-2)}{6} d_1^3 e^{-3i(\frac{\lambda}{\beta})} \cos^3\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right), \quad (12)$$

Where

$$D = ([3]_q + [2]_q - 2).$$

Similarly we take

$$e^{i\lambda \frac{\omega \partial_q h(\omega)}{h(\omega)}} = G(\omega) \quad (z \in E, -\frac{\pi}{2}\beta < \lambda < \frac{\pi}{2}\beta), \quad (13)$$

Where $G(\omega)$ is Analytic in E and Satisfies

$$G(0) = e^{i\lambda} \text{ and } |\arg G(\omega)| < \frac{\pi}{2}\beta, (\omega \in E).$$

The function $q(\omega)$ defined by

$$G(\omega)^{\frac{1}{\beta}} = \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)q(\omega) + i \sin\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right), (\omega \in E).$$

Is a Member of the class \mathcal{P} . Let $q(\omega) = 1 + c_1\omega + c_2\omega^2 + \dots, (\omega \in E)$.

By comparing coefficient in (13), we have

$$-a_2 = \frac{\beta c_1 e^{-i(\frac{\lambda}{\beta})}}{[2]_q - 1} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right), \quad (14)$$

$$(2[3]_q - [2]_q - 1)a_2^2 - ([3]_q - 1)a_3 = \beta c_2 e^{-i(\frac{\lambda}{\beta})} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) + \frac{\beta(\beta-1)}{2} c_1^2 e^{-i2(\frac{\lambda}{\beta})} \cos^2\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right), \quad (15)$$

$$-(T a_2 a_3 + ([4]_q - 1)a_4) = \beta c_3 e^{-i(\frac{\lambda}{\beta})} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) + \beta(\beta-1) c_1 c_2 e^{-2i(\frac{\lambda}{\beta})} \cos^2\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) + \frac{\beta(\beta-1)(\beta-2)}{6} c_1^3 e^{-3i(\frac{\lambda}{\beta})} \cos^3\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right). \quad (16)$$

Where

$$T = (5[4]_q - 2[3]_q - [2]_q - 2)a_2^3 - (5[4]_q - [3]_q - [2]_q - 3).$$

From (10) and (14) we have

$$c_1 = -d_1. \quad (17)$$

We shall obtain a refined estimate on $|d_1|$ for use in the estimates of $|a_3|$ and $|a_4|$. For this purpose we first add (11) with (15), then use the relations (17) and get the following:

$$(2([3]_q - [2]_q)a_2^2 = \beta(d_2 + c_2)e^{-i(\frac{\lambda}{\beta})} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) + \frac{\beta(\beta-1)}{2}(d_1^2 + c_1^2)e^{-i2(\frac{\lambda}{\beta})} \cos^2\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right).$$

Putting $a_2 = \frac{\beta d_1 e^{-i(\frac{\lambda}{\beta})}}{[2]_q - 1} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)$ from (10) we have after simplification:

$$d_1^2 = \frac{([2]_q - 1)^2 (d_2 + c_2)}{((2[3]_q - [2]_q^2 - 1)\beta + ([2]_q - 1)^2) e^{-i(\frac{\lambda}{\beta})} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)}.$$

By applying the familiar inequalities $|d_2| \leq 2$ and $|c_2| \leq 2$ we get:

$$\begin{aligned} |d_1| &\leq \sqrt{\frac{4([2]_q - 1)^2}{((2[3]_q - [2]_q^2 - 1)\beta + ([2]_q - 1)^2) \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)}} \\ &= \frac{2([2]_q - 1)}{\sqrt{((2[3]_q - [2]_q^2 - 1)\beta + ([2]_q - 1)^2) \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)}} \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

and

$$|a_2| \leq \frac{\beta |d_1| \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)}{[2]_q - 1} = \frac{2\beta}{\sqrt{((2[3]_q - [2]_q^2 - 1)\beta + ([2]_q - 1)^2) \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)}} \sqrt{\cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)}.$$

We next find a bound on $|a_3|$. For this we subtract (15) from (11) and get

$$2([3]_q - 1)a_3 = 2([3]_q - 1)a_2^2 + \beta(d_2 - c_2)e^{-i(\frac{\lambda}{\beta})} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) + \frac{\beta(\beta-1)}{2}(d_1^2 - c_1^2)e^{-i2(\frac{\lambda}{\beta})} \cos^2\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right).$$

The relation $d_1^2 = c_1^2$ from (17), reduces the above expression to

$$2([3]_q - 1)a_3 = 2([3]_q - 1)a_2^2 + \beta(d_2 - c_2)e^{-i(\frac{\lambda}{\beta})} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right). \quad (20)$$

Using $a_2 = \frac{\beta c_1 e^{-i(\frac{\lambda}{\beta})}}{[2]_q - 1} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)$ and (18), we get

$$\begin{aligned} 2([3]_q - 1)a_3 &= \frac{2([3]_q - 1)}{([2]_q - 1)^2} \beta^2 d_1^2 e^{-i2(\frac{\lambda}{\beta})} \cos^2\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) + \beta(d_2 - c_2)e^{-i(\frac{\lambda}{\beta})} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) \\ &= \frac{2([3]_q - 1)}{([2]_q - 1)^2} \beta^2 \left(\frac{([2]_q - 1)^2 (d_2 + c_2) e^{-i2(\frac{\lambda}{\beta})}}{((2[3]_q - [2]_q^2 - 1)\beta + ([2]_q - 1)^2) e^{-i(\frac{\lambda}{\beta})} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos^2\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) \right) + \\ &= K, \\ &= \frac{\beta}{((2[3]_q - [2]_q^2 - 1)\beta + ([2]_q - 1)^2)} [M d_2 + ((2[3]_q - [2]_q^2 - 1)\beta - ([2]_q - 1)^2) c_2] e^{-i(\frac{\lambda}{\beta})} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right), \end{aligned}$$

Where

$$K = \beta(d_2 - c_2)e^{-i\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right),$$

$$M = ((4[3]_q - [2]_q^2 - 3)\beta + ([2]_q - 1)^2)$$

Therefore, the inequalities $|d_2| \leq 2$ and $|c_2| \leq 2$ give the following: $2([3]_q - 1)|a_3|$

$$\leq \begin{cases} \frac{2\beta}{((2]_q - 1)^2 + (2[3]_q - [2]_q^2 - 1)\beta)} ((4[3]_q - [2]_q^2 - 3)\beta + 2([2]_q - 1)^2 - ([2]_q^2 - 1)\beta) \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right), & 0 \leq \beta \leq \frac{[2]_q - 1}{[2]_q + 1}, \\ \frac{2\beta}{((2]_q - 1)^2 + (2[3]_q - [2]_q^2 - 1)\beta)} ((4[3]_q - [2]_q^2 - 3)\beta + ([2]_q^2 - 1)\beta) \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right), & \frac{[2]_q - 1}{[2]_q + 1} \leq \beta \leq 1. \end{cases}$$

Which Simplifies

$$|a_3| \leq \begin{cases} \frac{2\beta}{[3]_q - 1} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right), & 0 \leq \beta \leq \frac{[2]_q - 1}{[2]_q + 1}; \\ \frac{4\beta^2}{((2]_q - 1)^2 + (2[3]_q - [2]_q^2 - 1)\beta)} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right), & \frac{[2]_q - 1}{[2]_q + 1} \leq \beta \leq 1. \end{cases}$$

Now we find an estimate on $|a_4|$. At first we shall derive a relation connecting d_1, d_2, d_3, c_2 and c_3 . To this end, Now we collect (12) and (16) we get

$$M(-a_2^3 + a_2a_3) = \beta(d_3 + c_3)e^{-i\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) + \beta(\beta - 1)(d_1d_2 + c_1c_2)e^{-i2\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos^2\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) + \frac{\beta(\beta - 1)}{6}(d_1^3 + c_1^3)e^{-i3\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos^3\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right), \tag{21}$$

Where

$$M = (5[4]_q - 2([3]_q + [2]_q) - 1).$$

Now we are putting $c_1 = -d_1$ in (21) we get

$$M(-a_2^3 + a_2a_3) = \beta(d_3 + c_3)e^{-i\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) + \beta(\beta - 1)d_1(d_2 - c_2)e^{-i2\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos^2\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right), \tag{22}$$

Where

$$M = (5[4]_q - 2([3]_q + [2]_q) - 1)$$

Substituting $a_3 = a_2^2 + \frac{\beta}{2([3]_q - 1)}(d_2 - c_2)e^{-i\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)$ from (20) in (21) we get after simplification:

$$(5[4]_q - 2([3]_q + [2]_q) - 1) \frac{\beta}{2([3]_q - 1)}(d_2 - c_2)e^{-i\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) = \beta(d_3 + c_3)e^{-i\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) + \beta(\beta - 1)d_1(d_2 - c_2)e^{-i2\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos^2\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)$$

Since $a_2 = \frac{\beta a_1}{[2]_q - 1} e^{-i\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)$, we have

SINCE $a_2 = \frac{\beta a_1}{[2]_q - 1} e^{-i\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)$, WE HAVE

$$\frac{M\beta^2}{2([3]_q - 1)} d_1(d_2 - c_2) e^{-i2\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos^2\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) = \beta(d_3 + c_3) e^{-i\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) + \beta(\beta - 1) d_1(d_2 - c_2) e^{-i2\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos^2\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right),$$

Where

$$M = (5[4]_q - 2([3]_q + [2]_q) - 1).$$

$$d_1(d_2 - c_2) = \frac{2([3]_q - 1)(d_3 + c_3) e^{i\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)}{(5[4]_q - 4[3]_q - 2[2]_q + 1)\beta + 2([3]_q - 1)}. \tag{23}$$

Or

$$2([4]_q - 1)a_4 = -(5[4]_q - 2[3]_q - 3)a_2^3 + 5([4]_q - 1)a_2a_3 + \beta(d_3 - c_3) e^{-i\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) + \beta(\beta - 1)(d_1d_2 - c_1c_2) e^{-i2\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos^2\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) + \frac{\beta(\beta-1)(\beta-2)}{6} (d_1^3 - c_1^3) e^{-i3\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos^3\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right).$$

Observing that $c_1 = -d_1$ we have $d_1^3 - c_1^3 = 2d_1^3$ and therefore

$$2([4]_q - 1)a_4 = -(5[4]_q - 2([3]_q + [2]_q) - 1)a_2^3 + (5[4]_q - 2([3]_q + [2]_q) - 1)a_2a_3 - (2[2]_q - 2)a_2^3 + 2([3]_q + [2]_q - 2)a_2a_3 + \beta(d_3 - c_3) e^{-i\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) + \beta(\beta - 1)d_1(d_2 + c_2) e^{-i2\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos^2\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) + \frac{\beta(\beta-1)(\beta-2)}{3} d_1^3 e^{-i3\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos^3\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right).$$

We Replace

$$-(5[4]_q - 2([3]_q + [2]_q) - 1)a_2^3 + (5[4]_q - 2([3]_q + [2]_q) - 1)a_2a_3$$

By the right hand side of (22) ,

$$\text{put } a_3 = a_2^2 + \frac{\beta}{2([3]_q - 1)} (d_2 - c_2) e^{-i\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)$$

$$\text{and } a_2 = \frac{\beta d_1 e^{-i\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)}{([2]_q - 1)}.$$

This gives

$$\begin{aligned}
 2([4]_q - 1)a_4 &= \beta(d_3 + c_3)e^{-i\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) + \beta(\beta - 1)d_1(d_2 - c_2)e^{-i2\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos^2\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) \\
 &+ H \frac{\beta d_1 e^{-i\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)}{([2]_q - 1)} \left(\frac{\beta^2 d_1^2 e^{-2i\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos^2\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)}{([2]_q - 1)^2} + \frac{\beta}{2([3]_q - 1)} (d_2 - c_2) e^{-i\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) \right) \\
 &+ \beta(d_3 - c_3)e^{-i\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) + \beta(\beta - 1)d_1(d_2 + c_2)e^{-i2\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos^2\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) \\
 &- \frac{2\beta^3 d_1^3 e^{-3i\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos^3\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)}{([2]_q - 1)^3} + \frac{\beta(\beta - 1)(\beta - 2)}{3} d_1^3 e^{-i3\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos^3\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) \\
 &= 2\beta d_3 e^{-i\frac{\lambda}{\beta}} \cos\frac{\lambda}{\beta} + \frac{\beta([3]_q[2]_q - 1)\beta - ([3]_q[2]_q - [2]_q - [3]_q + 1)}{([3]_q - 1)([2]_q - 1)^3} d_1(d_2 - c_2) e^{-2i\frac{\lambda}{\beta}} \cos^2\frac{\lambda}{\beta} \\
 &+ \beta(\beta - 1)d_1(d_2 + c_2) e^{-2i\frac{\lambda}{\beta}} \cos^2\frac{\lambda}{\beta} + \frac{N\beta^3 - B\beta^2 + 2([2]_q - 1)^3\beta}{3([2]_q - 1)^3} d_1^3 e^{-3i\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right),
 \end{aligned}$$

Where

$$\begin{aligned}
 H &= 2([3]_q + [2]_q - 2) \\
 N &= (6([3]_q + [2]_q - 3) + ([2]_q - 1)^3) \\
 B &= 3([2]_q - 1)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

Next, replacing $d_1(d_2 - c_2)$ by the expression in the right hand side of (23) and c_1^2 by (18) we finally get

$$\begin{aligned}
 2([4]_q - 1)a_4 &= \frac{\beta([3]_q[2]_q - 1)\beta - ([3]_q[2]_q - [2]_q - [3]_q + 1)}{([3]_q - 1)([2]_q - 1)^3} \frac{2([3]_q - 1)(d_1 + c_1) e^{-i\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)}{(5[4]_q - 4[3]_q - 2[2]_q + 1)\beta + 2([3]_q - 1)} \\
 &+ 2\beta d_3 e^{-i\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) + \beta(\beta - 1)d_1(d_2 + c_2) e^{-2i\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos^2\frac{\lambda}{\beta} \\
 &+ \frac{(6([3]_q + [2]_q - 3) + ([2]_q - 1)^3)\beta^2 - 2([2]_q - 1)^3\beta}{3([2]_q - 1)^3} \frac{([2]_q - 1)^2(d_1 + c_1)}{([2]_q - 1) + 2([3]_q - [2]_q - 1)\beta} d_1 e^{-2i\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos^2\frac{\lambda}{\beta} - 2\beta d_3 e^{-i\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos\frac{\lambda}{\beta} + \frac{2\beta([3]_q[2]_q - 1)\beta - ([3]_q[2]_q - [2]_q - [3]_q + 1)}{([3]_q - 1)([2]_q - 1)^3} (d_2 + c_2) e^{-i\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) + \frac{2([3]_q[2]_q - 1)\beta - 2([3]_q - [2]_q - [3]_q + 1)\beta^2 - ([2]_q - 1)^3\beta}{3([2]_q - 1)([2]_q - 1)^2 + 2([3]_q - [2]_q - 1)} d_1(d_2 + c_2) e^{-2i\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos^2\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) \\
 &= \beta \left[\frac{2([2]_q - 1)^3(5[4]_q + [2]_q[3]_q - 4[3]_q - 2[2]_q)\beta + (3[3]_q - [3]_q[2]_q + [2]_q - 3)}{([2]_q - 1)^3(5[4]_q - 4[3]_q - 2[2]_q + 1)\beta + 2([3]_q - 1)} d_3 \right. \\
 &\left. + \frac{2\beta([3]_q[2]_q - 1)\beta - ([3]_q[2]_q - [2]_q - [3]_q + 1)}{([2]_q - 1)(5[4]_q - 4[3]_q - 2[2]_q + 1)\beta + 2([3]_q - 1)} c_3 + \frac{2(3[3]_q[2]_q + 3[2]_q - [2]_q^2 - 8)\beta^2 - H}{3([2]_q - 1)(([2]_q - 1)^2 + 2([3]_q - [2]_q - 1))} d_1(d_2 + d_3) \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) \right] e^{-i\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right),
 \end{aligned}$$

Where $H = 3([2]_q - 1)(2[3]_q - [2]_q^2 - 1)\beta - ([2]_q - 1)^3$.

This Gives

$$\begin{aligned}
 |a_4| &\leq \frac{\beta}{2([4]_q - 1)} \left[\left| \frac{2((5[4]_q + [2]_q[3]_q - 4[3]_q - 2[2]_q)\beta + (3[3]_q - [3]_q[2]_q + [2]_q - 3))}{((5[4]_q - 4[3]_q - 2[2]_q + 1)\beta + 2([3]_q - 1))} |d_3| \right. \right. \\
 &+ \left. \left| \frac{2((3[3]_q[2]_q - 1)\beta - ([3]_q[2]_q - [2]_q - [3]_q + 1))}{([2]_q - 1)^3(5[4]_q - 4[3]_q - 2[2]_q + 1)\beta + 2([3]_q - 1)} |c_3| \right. \right. \\
 &\left. \left. + \left| \frac{2(3[3]_q[2]_q + 3[2]_q - [2]_q^2 - 8)\beta^2 - H}{3([2]_q - 1)(([2]_q - 1)^2 + 2([3]_q - [2]_q - 1))} |d_1| |d_2 + d_3| \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) \right| \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

Where $H = 3([2]_q - 1)(2[3]_q - [2]_q^2 - 1)\beta - ([2]_q - 1)^3$.

$$|a_4| \leq \begin{cases} \frac{2\beta}{[4]_q-1} \left[\frac{2((5[4]_q+[2]_q[3]_q-4[3]_q-2[2]_q)\beta+(3[3]_q-[3]_q[2]_q+[2]_q-3))}{((5[4]_q-4[3]_q-2[2]_q+1)\beta+2([3]_q-1))} + A_2 + A_1 \sqrt{\cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)}, & 0 < \beta < A; \\ \frac{2\beta}{[4]_q-1} \left[\frac{2((5[4]_q+[2]_q[3]_q-4[3]_q-2[2]_q)\beta+(3[3]_q-[3]_q[2]_q+[2]_q-3))}{((5[4]_q-4[3]_q-2[2]_q+1)\beta+2([3]_q-1))} + A_2 - A_1 \sqrt{\cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)}, & A \leq \beta < A_4; \\ \frac{2\beta}{[4]_q-1} \left[\frac{2((5[4]_q+[2]_q[3]_q-4[3]_q-2[2]_q)\beta+(3[3]_q-[3]_q[2]_q+[2]_q-3))}{((5[4]_q-4[3]_q-2[2]_q+1)\beta+2([3]_q-1))} + A_2 + A_1 \sqrt{\cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)}, & A_4 \leq \beta \leq 1. \end{cases} \tag{24}$$

$$A = \frac{3([2]_q-1)(2[3]_q-[2]_q^2-1) + \sqrt{(36[3]_q^2+[2]_q^4+42[2]_q^2+8[2]_q^3+73) - (12[3]_q[2]_q^2-36[3]_q-88[2]_q-24[3]_q[2]_q)}}{4(3[3]_q[2]_q+3[2]_q-[2]_q^2-8)}$$

Where

$$A_1 = \frac{2(2(3[3]_q[2]_q+3[2]_q-[2]_q^2-8)\beta^2-3([2]_q-1)(2[3]_q-[2]_q^2-1)\beta-([2]_q-1)^3)}{3([2]_q-1)\sqrt{((2[2]_q-1)^2+(2[3]_q-[2]_q^2-1))}}$$

$$A_2 = \frac{([3]_q[2]_q-[2]_q-[3]_q+1)-2([3]_q[2]_q-1)\beta}{([2]_q-1)^2(5[4]_q-4[3]_q-2[2]_q+1)\beta+2([3]_q-1)}$$

$$A_3 = \frac{2((3[3]_q[2]_q-1)\beta-([3]_q[2]_q-[2]_q-[3]_q+1))}{([2]_q-1)^3(5[4]_q-4[3]_q-2[2]_q+1)\beta+2([3]_q-1)}$$

$$A_4 = \frac{([3]_q[2]_q-[2]_q-[3]_q+1)}{[3]_q[2]_q}$$

By applying the inequalities $|d_n| \leq 2, |c_n| \leq 2 (n = 2,3)$ we get

$$|a_4| \leq \begin{cases} \frac{2\beta}{[4]_q-1} \left[1 - \frac{2}{3} A_1 \sqrt{\cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \right], & 0 < \beta < A; \\ \frac{2\beta}{[4]_q-1} \left[1 + \frac{2}{3} A_1 \sqrt{\cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \right], & A \leq \beta < A_4; \\ \frac{2\beta}{[4]_q-1} \left[\frac{([2]_q-1)^3(5[4]_q+2[3]_q[2]_q-4[3]_q-2[2]_q-1)+L}{([2]_q-1)^3(5[4]_q-4[3]_q-2[2]_q+1)\beta+2([3]_q-1)} + \frac{2}{3} A_1 \sqrt{\cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \right], & A_4 \leq \beta \leq 1, \end{cases}$$

Where

$$L = (2([3]_q + [2]_q) - ([3]_q[2]_q + 4))$$

$$A = \frac{3([2]_q-1)(2[3]_q-[2]_q^2-1) + \sqrt{(36[3]_q^2+[2]_q^4+42[2]_q^2+8[2]_q^3+73) - (12[3]_q[2]_q^2-36[3]_q-88[2]_q-24[3]_q[2]_q)}}{4(3[3]_q[2]_q+3[2]_q-[2]_q^2-8)}$$

$$A_1 = \frac{2(2(3[3]_q[2]_q + 3[2]_q - [2]_q^3 - 8)\beta^2 - 3([2]_q - 1)(2[3]_q - [2]_q^2 - 1)\beta - ([2]_q - 1)^3)}{3([2]_q - 1)^3 \sqrt{([2]_q - 1)^2 + (2[3]_q - [2]_q^2 - 1)}} A_4$$

$$= \frac{([3]_q[2]_q - [2]_q - [3]_q + 1)}{[3]_q[2]_q}$$

As $q \rightarrow 1^-$ in the above Theorem we get the following:

➤ Corollary 2.1 [21] Let $f(z) = z + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} a_n z^n$ be in $\lambda\text{-SP}_{\Sigma_{\Theta}}^{\beta}$, ($|\lambda| \leq \frac{\pi}{2}$, $0 \leq \beta < 1$). Then

$$|a_2| \leq \frac{2\beta}{\sqrt{\beta+1}} \sqrt{\cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)}, \quad (25)$$

$$|a_3| \leq \begin{cases} \beta \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right), & 0 \leq \beta \leq \frac{1}{2}, \\ \frac{4\beta^2}{1+\beta} \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right), & \frac{1}{2} \leq \beta \leq 1. \end{cases} \quad (26)$$

$$|a_4| \leq \begin{cases} \frac{2\beta}{3} \left[1 - \frac{2}{3} \frac{16\beta^2 - 3\beta - 1}{\sqrt[3]{1+\beta}} \sqrt{\cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \right], & 0 < \beta < \frac{3+\sqrt{73}}{32}; \\ \frac{2\beta}{3} \left[1 + \frac{2}{3} \frac{16\beta^2 - 3\beta - 1}{\sqrt[3]{1+\beta}} \sqrt{\cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \right], & \frac{3+\sqrt{73}}{32} \leq \beta < 1; \\ \frac{2\beta}{3} \left[\frac{15\beta}{5\beta} + \frac{2}{3} \frac{16\beta^2 - 3\beta - 1}{\sqrt[3]{1+\beta}} \sqrt{\cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right) \cos\left(\frac{\lambda}{\beta}\right)} \right], & \frac{2}{5} \leq \beta \leq 1. \end{cases} \quad (27)$$

➤ Theorem 2.2 Let $f(z)$, given by (1) in the class $SP_{\Sigma_{\Theta}}(\sigma, q)$, ($|\lambda| \leq \frac{\pi}{2}$, $0 \leq \sigma < 1$). Then

$$|a_2| \leq \sqrt{\frac{2(1-\sigma)\cos\lambda}{([3]_q - [2]_q)}} \quad (28)$$

$$|a_3| \leq \frac{2(1-\sigma)\cos\lambda}{[3]_q - [2]_q} \quad (29)$$

and

$$|a_4| \leq \frac{2(1-\sigma)\cos\lambda}{[4]_q - 1} \left[1 + \frac{5[4]_q - [3]_q - 4}{([3]_q - [2]_q)\cos\lambda} \sqrt{\frac{2(1-\sigma)}{([3]_q - [2]_q)\cos\lambda}} \right]. \quad (30)$$

Proof. Let $f \in SP_{\Sigma_{\Theta}}(\sigma, q)$, then by Definition 1.1 we have

$$e^{-i\lambda} \frac{z \partial_q f(z)}{f(z)} = Q_1(z) \cos\lambda + i \sin\lambda \quad (31)$$

and

$$e^{-i\lambda} \frac{\omega \partial_q h(\omega)}{h(\omega)} = P_1(\omega) \cos\lambda + i \sin\lambda \quad (32)$$

Where $\Re(Q_1(z)) > \sigma$,

$$Q_1(z) = 1 + d_1z + d_2z^2 + \dots (z \in E)$$

and $\Re(P_1(\omega)) > \sigma$,

$$P_1(\omega) = 1 + c_1\omega + c_2\omega^2 + \dots (\omega \in E).$$

As in the proof of Theorem 2.1, by suitably comparing coefficient in (31) and (32) we have

$$a_2 e^{-i\lambda} = \frac{d_1 \cos \lambda}{[2]_q - 1} \quad (33)$$

$$d_2 \cos \lambda, \quad \left(([3]_q - 1)a_2 - ([2]_q - 1)a_2^2 \right) e^{-i\lambda} = \quad (34)$$

$$\left(([4]_q - 1)a_4 - H a_2 a_3 + ([2]_q - 1)a_2^3 \right) e^{-i\lambda} = d_3 \cos \lambda. \quad (35)$$

Where $H = ([3]_q + [2]_q - 2)$ and

$$-a_2 e^{-i\lambda} = \frac{c_1 \cos \lambda}{[2]_q - 1} \quad (36)$$

$$c_2 \cos \lambda, \quad \left(2[3]_q - [2]_q - 1 \right) a_2^2 - ([3]_q - 1) a_2 e^{-i\lambda} = \quad (37)$$

$$-(R + ([4]_q - 1)a_4) e^{-i\lambda} = c_3 \cos \lambda, \quad (38)$$

Where

$$R = (5[4]_q - 2[3]_q - [2]_q - 2)a_2^3 - (5[4]_q - [3]_q - [2]_q - 3)a_2 a_3.$$

In order to express d_1 in terms of d_2 and c_2 we first add (34) and (37) and get

$$2([3]_q - [2]_q) a_2^2 = (d_2 + c_2) \frac{\cos \lambda}{e^{i\lambda}}. \quad (39)$$

Again putting $a_2 e^{i\lambda} = \frac{d_1 \cos \lambda}{[2]_q - 1}$ from (33) we have

$$\frac{2([3]_q - [2]_q) d_1^2 \cos \lambda}{([2]_q - 1)^2 e^{2i\lambda}} = (d_2 + c_2) \frac{\cos \lambda}{e^{i\lambda}}$$

Or equivalently

$$d_1^2 = (d_2 + c_2) \frac{([2]_q - 1)^2 e^{i\lambda}}{2([3]_q - [2]_q) \cos \lambda} \quad (40)$$

The familiar inequalities $|d_2| \leq 2(1 - \sigma)$, $|c_2| \leq 2(1 - \sigma)$ yield

$$|d_1|^2 = \frac{2([2]_q - 1)^2 (1 - \sigma)}{([3]_q - [2]_q) \cos \lambda}$$

Which Implies that

$$\begin{aligned}
 |d_1| &= \sqrt{\frac{2([2]_q-1)^2(1-\sigma)}{([3]_q-[2]_q)\cos\lambda}} \\
 \text{and } |a_2| &\leq \frac{|d_2|\cos\lambda}{[2]_q-1} \\
 &\leq \sqrt{\frac{2(1-\sigma)}{([3]_q-[2]_q)\cos\lambda}} \cos\lambda = \sqrt{\frac{2(1-\sigma)\cos\lambda}{([3]_q-[2]_q)}}.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{41}$$

Following the Lines of Proof of Theorem 2.1, with Appropriate Changes, we Get that

$$2([3]_q - 1)a_3 = \left(\frac{[3]_q}{([3]_q-[2]_q)} d_2 + \frac{([3]_q-2)}{([3]_q-[2]_q)} c_2 \right) \frac{\cos\lambda}{e^{i\lambda}}$$

The inequalities $|d_2| \leq 2(1 - \sigma), |c_2| \leq 2(1 - \sigma)$ yield

$$|a_3| \leq \frac{2(1-\sigma)\cos\lambda}{[3]_q-[2]_q} \tag{42}$$

We shall next find an estimate on $|a_4|$, By subtracting (38) from (35) we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 2([4]_q - 1)a_4 &= -(5[4]_q - 2[3]_q - 3)a_2^3 + 5([4]_q - \\
 &1)a_2a_3 + (d_3 - c_3) \frac{\cos\lambda}{e^{i\lambda}}
 \end{aligned}$$

A substitution of the value of a_2 from the relation (33) gives

$$\begin{aligned}
 2([4]_q - 1)a_4 &= -(5[4]_q - 2[3]_q - 3)d_1^3 \frac{\cos^3\lambda}{([2]_q-1)^3 e^{3i\lambda}} + \\
 &5([4]_q - 1)d_1 \frac{\cos\lambda}{([2]_q-1)e^{i\lambda}} a_3 + (d_3 - c_3) \frac{\cos\lambda}{e^{i\lambda}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, using the inequalities $|d_3| \leq 2(1 - \sigma), |c_3| \leq 2(1 - \sigma)$, the estimate for $|d_1|$ from (41) and the estimate for $|a_3|$ from (42), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 2([4]_q - 1)|a_4| &\leq (5[4]_q - 2[3]_q - 3)|d_1^3| \frac{\cos^3\lambda}{([2]_q-1)^3} + 5([4]_q - 1)|d_1| \frac{\cos\lambda}{([2]_q-1)} |a_3| + |d_3 - c_3| \cos\lambda \\
 &\leq (5[4]_q - 2[3]_q - 3) \sqrt{\frac{2(1-\sigma)}{([3]_q-[2]_q)\cos\lambda}} \frac{2(1-\sigma)}{[3]_q-[2]_q} \cos^2\lambda \\
 &+ 5([4]_q - 1) \sqrt{\frac{2(1-\sigma)}{([3]_q-[2]_q)\cos\lambda}} \frac{2(1-\sigma)}{([3]_q-[2]_q)} \cos^2\lambda + 4(1 - \sigma) \cos\lambda \\
 &\leq 4(1 - \sigma) \cos\lambda \left[1 + \frac{5[4]_q - [3]_q - 4}{([3]_q-[2]_q)} \sqrt{\frac{2(1-\sigma)\cos\lambda}{([3]_q-[2]_q)}} \right].
 \end{aligned}$$

Or equivalently,

$$|a_4| \leq \frac{2(1-\sigma)\cos\lambda}{[4]_q-1} \left[1 + \frac{5[4]_q - [3]_q - 4}{([3]_q-[2]_q)} \sqrt{\frac{2(1-\sigma)\cos\lambda}{([3]_q-[2]_q)}} \right].$$

As $q \rightarrow 1^-$ in the above Theorem we get the following:

➤ Corollary 2.2 [21] Let $f(z)$, given by (1) in the class $\mathcal{SP}_{\Sigma, \Theta}(\sigma)$, ($|\lambda| \leq \frac{\pi}{2}, 0 \leq \sigma < 1$). then

$$\begin{aligned}
 |a_2| &\leq \sqrt{2(1-\sigma)\cos\lambda} \\
 |a_3| &\leq 2(1-\sigma)\cos\lambda \\
 |a_4| &\leq \frac{2(1-\sigma)\cos\lambda}{3} [1 + 13\sqrt{2(1-\sigma)\cos\lambda}].
 \end{aligned}$$

II. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we introduced and investigated two new subclasses of the function class $\Sigma @$ of λ - q -bi-spirallike functions defined in the open unit disc. Furthermore, We find estimates on the coefficients $|a_2|$, $|a_3|$ and $|a_4|$ for functions in these two new subclasses for functions. Future work making use of the values of a_2 , a_3 and a_4 we can calculate Hankel determinant coefficient for the bi-spirallike function classes.

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